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SOCIAL MEDIA BULLYING EXPERIENCES AND COPYING MECHANISMS AMONG THE SOUTH AFRICAN YOUTH POPULATION

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Abstract

Despite its crucial role in enhancing communication, social media has come with a host of unwanted actions as citizens converge on a less regulated cyberspace. Bullying has been one of the unintended consequences of social media usage, especially among the youth population. This study explored bullying experiences on social media and its effects on youth in selected King Sabata Dalindyebo local municipality areas of South Africa. The study used a mixed methods approach where data was collected using questionnaires and in-depth interviews from a sample of 115 questionnaire participants consisting of youth aged 18-35, and 5 participants for in-depth interviews. Findings revealed that social media bullying mainly manifests through rude messages from fake accounts on social media accounts, as well as being called by nasty names such as loser and idiot; being heavily criticised for posts on social media platforms; false rumours on social media platforms; and sharing of sexually explicit pictures without the victims' consent. Feeling upset, anxiety, depression and loss of self-confidence were found to be the leading effects of bullying on social media platforms. Online vigilance, security and privacy consciousness, and psycho-social support from the family were regarded as the copying mechanisms for social media bullying.

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Introduction

Social media, defined by Kietzmann et al. (2011) as “interactive technologies and digital channels that create and share information, ideas, interests, and other forms of expression through virtual communities and networks”, has changed every facet of people’s lives. Social media platforms are among the leading social network applications that the youth primarily use. WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter, TikTok, Instagram, and YouTube are the most used social network platforms that have transformed media systems, irrevocably altering dynamics of production, consumption, and dissemination of information (Mugari & Muzinda, 2021; Mugari & Chisuvi, 2020). These platforms are used for texting, voice, images, and videos. Moreover, users can follow or be followed by others, arrangements that facilitate the instantaneous dissemination of content and display “viral” qualities, where information can rapidly, and often unpredictably, cascade across networks (Mugari, 2020). Obar and Wildman (2015) state that the media, a modern trend in information and knowledge distribution, has taken communication beyond the limits of traditional communication and socialising, making it a vital part of people’s lives, affecting their social and economic activities. The wide adoption of social media platforms for communication was heightened during the COVID-19 era, when physical interaction was either limited or prohibited.

Notwithstanding the immense benefits of social media platforms, the platforms have had negative impacts, especially among the youth population. One of the manifestations of the ugly side of social media is bullying. Bullying is seen as the use of force, cruel mocking, threat, or intimidation intended to hurt another individual physically, mentally, or emotionally (Whittaker & Kowalski, 2015). Traditional bullying is when there are physical fights with the victim, name-calling, and spreading rumours about the victim. However, bullying has evolved with the advent of technological capabilities such as social media platforms, as well as widespread use of cell phones and other portable devices connected to the internet. With the new capabilities of technology-enhanced social engineering, traditional bullying has evolved to cyberbullying. According to Besley (2019), cyberbullying involves the use of digital technologies to harass, threaten, or humiliate another person. Such digital technologies can

include instant messaging, social media, or defamatory personal websites that encourage deliberate, repeated, and hostile behaviour by an individual or group intended to harm others (Besley, 2019).

It is widely noted that youth have the highest social media usage rates, as they spend most of their time on social media. For example, Mhlomi & Osunkunle (2017) demonstrate that the youth from all over South Africa are using social media and creating content that encourages riches or material wealth and in the process setting out unrealistic expectations of what life is supposed to be. The youth seek validation from others, and they go to the extent of using filters to change the public's perception of who they (Treem et al., 2016). It is during these online social networking activities that incidents of cyberbullying manifest.

This study explored the scourge of cyberbullying among the youth population in South Africa. The study was guided by the following objectives: a) to examine the experiences of being bullied over social media; b) To examine the effects of bullying on the youth; and c) to determine mechanisms of coping with bullying on social media. The study comes against the background of a rise in cyberbullying among the youth population in South Africa, with negative consequences on the mental and physical wellbeing upon the victims. The study provides an in-depth analysis of the magnitude of the problem of cyberbullying, which will guide policy makers to craft prescriptive measures from an informed perspective. By articulating the effects of cyberbullying, findings will also provide a reference point to the youth and parents on the need to guard against scourge. Moreover, as part of the conclusion, the study proffers some prescriptive measures to deal with cyberbullying.

Social media and the youth

Social media comes in various forms which include, social networking (e.g. Facebook), instant messaging (e.g. WhatsApp), photo and video sharing (e.g. Instagram and YouTube), or micro-blogging (e.g. Twitter) sites (Walsh & O'Connor, 2019). In contrast with traditional media, social media platforms are distributed and participatory systems of communication where those formerly known as audience emerge as producers of large quantities of "user generated content" (Mugari, 2020). Through social media platforms, users can follow or be followed by others, arrangements that facilitate the instantaneous dissemination of content and display "viral"

qualities, where information can rapidly, and often unpredictably, cascade across networks (Yar, 2014). It is widely believed that youth consume more of their time on the internet than watching TV or spending time with their families.

The youth utilize social networking sites for various purposes, including chatting with friends, killing time, studying topics outside of the classroom, and boosting self-esteem when feeling low (Seo et al., 2013). Complementary reasons for joining social networking sites include: (a) peer pressure from others who have social media accounts; (b) dating; (c) expressing oneself while playing around with the identities they have, which encompass things like gender, sexual orientation, socioeconomic status and ethnic background; (d) the desire for belonging; and (e) establishing a personal area for close friendships (Seo et al., 2014; Livingstone, 2011; Siibank, 2009). Social media is more than just a means of communication and the youths' lives centre on technology use. One of the main traits of modern-day youth is their early and regular exposure to technology. Many youths are now growing up with smartphones and laptops and have become accustomed to using technology for social media and pleasure (Park & Gursoy, 2012). Youth use this period to examine and nurture their identities and personalities from infancy to maturity. Social media plays a vital part in shaping a youth's social circle and personality.

With research showing that the youth are the major players on various social networking platforms (Seo et al., 2014; Dube, 2016), a lot of benefits are derived from these social networking platforms. These benefits include chances to get involved in the community by volunteering and fundraising for charitable causes; improving one's own and group creativity through the creation and sharing of artistic and musical endeavours; growing one's ideas through the generation of blogs, podcasts, and gaming sites; and expanding one's online network by connecting with people who share desires and bringing people from a variety of cultures into one's community on the web (Boyd, 2008). Social networking platforms have been viewed to be helping many students settle, be updated, and engage in university life, with Debatin et al. (2009) further emphasising that a student's life without at least one social network may be difficult at university. Lehart et al.'s (2010) research revealed that youth have access to excellent health resources on a range of topics that are important to

them, including depression symptoms, stress management, and sexually transmitted infections (STIs).

Social media and bullying

The volume of personal information shared on social media, particularly on teen-focused social networking sites, has made it possible for cyberbullying to flourish. In the past two decades, cyberbullying has grown significantly in popularity among young people because it enables its victims to broadcast embarrassing content in front of their friends. Bullying is described as an aggressive act committed over time and frequently by a group or an individual towards another person who is unable to protect themselves (Bannink et al., 2014). A new type of bullying known as "cyberbullying" has emerged because of the usage of mobile phones and the Internet. Aggression via electronic means, the Internet, and particularly social media is known as cyberbullying (Bannink et al., 2014). According to Belsey (2006), cyberbullying is the intentional, persistent, and threatening conduct by oneself or a collective that aims to harm other people through the misuse of knowledge and interaction with technological advances, which include email, mobile devices, writing boards, chat rooms, blogs, games played online, and via the internet specific polling websites. Webster et al. (2017) simply defines cyberbullying as the unauthorized spreading of negative remarks against another person over the Internet.

Watts et al. (2017) list types of cyberbullying as follows: Flaming, which involves sending offensive or disgusting statements about the victim(s) publicly or directly to them; harassment, which entails persistently abusing and insulting the victim(s) via internet messaging; denigration which involves victims of cyberbullying getting disrespectful and fraudulent texts sent by the cyberbully; masquerading, in which the perpetrator allegedly assumes a different identity in order to disseminate damaging and menacing material to others about their targets or victims; and trickery, which occurs whenever a cyberbully coerces the target or the victims towards disclosing classified or confidential data and then makes that information publicly available. Notwithstanding the varying manifestations of cyberbullying, the perpetrators capitalise on online interaction, confidentiality, and quick dissemination of information over social networking sites to hurt the victims (Webster, 2017).

Effects of cyberbullying

Bullying, in all its manifestations, has detrimental effects on the victims. According to Ackers (2012), the severity of the effects of cyberbullying and the relatively easy way of carrying out acts of cyberbullying make this a social problem. Youth who are cyberbullied face risks of negative outcomes like distress, anger, lack of safety at school, loneliness, low self-esteem, weapons possession, and eating disorders (Jackson & Cohen, 2012; Dehue et al., 2008; Ybarra & Mitchell, 2007). Raskauskas and Stoltz (2007) state that youth who are cyberbullied are sad most of the time, and unwilling to attend school. Cains and Gradisar (2010), as well as Sourander et al., (2010) further note that victims of cyberbullying are at high risk of experiencing psychosomatic problems such as problems falling asleep at night and frequent headaches. Studies indicate that mental health issues such as despair, low self-esteem, anxiety, and academic phobias drive victims of cyberbullying to consider suicide (Faryadi, 2011; Juvonen & Gross 2008). Individuals who are the targets of online bullying are more likely to experience mental health issues such as social anxiety, apprehension depressive disorders, feeling isolated, low self-worth, and abysmal academic performance because they find it challenging to stay focused on their studies while under the intense psychological pressure of the harassment (Akcil, 2018). In addition, studies have also demonstrated that victims of cyberbullying encounter problems with both their mental and physical wellness as well as psychosocial problems, which include diminished dedication to their studies and other improper behaviour (Walker et al., 2011; Raskauskas and Stoltz, 2007). According to Faryadi (2011), cyberbullying victims go through intense psychological strain that makes it difficult for them to concentrate entirely on their academics. As a result, their academic achievement suffers since they are mentally wounded and are unable to flourish in their educational endeavours.

Social media also contributes to anxiety and sadness, and prolonged stress leads to anxiety and despair (Nesi & Printstein, 2015; Jacobs, 2014). Alden and Taylor (2021) further emphasized that individuals with social anxiety experience fear and anxiety in social situations in which they will be negatively evaluated or judged by others and may limit their opportunities to have meaningful social relationships. Being on continual guard for predators triggers the production of the stress hormone cortisol, as much as it does being on the lookout for fresh communications on social networks, which appeals to the nervous system's natural fight-or-flight response (Jacobs, 2014). Social media primarily encourages the youth to present a facade that emphasises all the joy, excitement, and success they seem to have, but says very little about their daily underlying struggles and creates a false sense of connection. Consequently, their profiles on social media platforms do not represent who they are but reflect how they want to be seen online. Tayyeba & Rjema (2019) also aver that late-night connectivity harms the youth's health, including bad feelings, higher tension, and sadness, especially if coupled by online encounters with predators such as cyberbullies.

Mechanisms for dealing with cyberbullying

According to Peled (2019), parental supervision and a heightened sense of adult punishment are linked to decreased engagement in cyberbullying. Therefore, parents must become more informed and conscious of what their kids do online. It is also critical to concentrate on altering social norms and ideas inside educational environments to influence youth's attitudes toward cyberbullying (Perren et al., 2012). Youths might not be prepared to embrace cyberbullying as an accepted practice or consider the matter seriously if social standards are changed (Perren et al., 2012). In order to stop cyberbullying, education and awareness regarding cyberbullying are essential (Walrave & Heirman, 2011). Perren et al. (2012) further state that educational institutions should restrict destructive online interactions, for instance, by letting students utilize computers or the Internet for good purposes only. As a result, youth will experience healthy interactions and favourable opinions about technology.

According to Tanrikulu (2015), any age can be affected by cyberbullying; therefore, attention must be paid to surveillance, including maintaining laptops and other electronic devices within visual reach. This also entails monitoring how technology and the Internet are used at home and in school settings. One of the most

important ways to stop cyberbullying is to teach youth preventative measures, such as knowing what kind of sensitive information to publish and setting limits on what may be shared online (Sticca et al., 2013).

Methodology

The study was conducted in Ward 5 in King Sabata Dalindyebo municipality. King Sabata Dalindyebo is a municipality situated in the inland of Eastern Cape province in South Africa. The Ward has a population of approximately 8,500 residents. This ward has the following locations: Myezo Park, Fortgale, Sidwadwa View, and Southridge. The study adopted a mixed method approach, wherein data were collected using a mainly closed-ended questionnaire and in-depth interviews. A sample of 115 respondents, comprising the 18 to 35 age-group, was selected for quantitative data using stratified random sampling. The population was stratified according to the four locations (Myezo Park, Fortgale, Sidwadwa View and Southridge) within the Ward and respondents were either randomly selected or selected using snowball sampling until the required number of respondents was reached. Walter Sisulu University students who reside in these locations were also included as respondents. Five (5) participants were purposely sampled for qualitative data and these included two Criminology lecturers, a psychologist, a social worker, and one police officer. They were selected based on their in-depth appreciation of the cyberbullying phenomenon. All the ethical protocols were observed, and the study was cleared by the Walter Sisulu University Faculty of Humanities, Social Sciences and Law Research Ethics Committee.

Instruments development and analysis

A closed-ended questionnaire was used to gather quantitative data. The questionnaire had four sections: Section A dealing with demographic data; Section B dealing with the experiences of cyberbullying; Section C dealt with the effects of cyberbullying; while Section D dealt with mechanisms for coping with cyberbullying. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyse the quantitative data and the data were then presented in tables which denoted frequencies, percentages and average. A semi-structured interview guide was used to gather qualitative data. Each interview session lasted between 30 to 45 minutes and the researchers took down notes during the interview sessions.

Qualitative data were analysed through thematic analysis and were used to complement the quantitative data.

Findings

Experiences of being bullied on social media

This section details the experiences of being bullied over social media. The experiences of being bullied over social media were listed, and the respondents were asked to indicate the correct answers by ticking from three responses- not at all, sometimes, or always. The respondent's responses are shown in Table 1.

Results on Table 1 reveal that a significant number of respondents (44%) have received rude messages from fake accounts on social media, with 38% indicating that they sometimes receive these rude messages and 6% indicating that they always receive these messages. This was followed by respondents who have been called by nasty names (loser, idiot, etc.,) on social media, and respondents who have been criticized because of a post they made on their timeline. The two forms of abuse had a total of 40% apiece of the respondents who indicate that they sometimes happened or always happened.

Table 1: Responses on experiences of being bullied over social media.

Statement	N	S	A	Total	Average
Have you ever received rude messages (for example, swearing) from fake accounts on social media?	64 (55.7)	44 (38.3)	7 (6.1)	115 (100)	1.50
Have you ever been subjected to false rumors on social media?	70 (60.9)	41 (35.7)	4 (3.5)	115 (100)	1.43
Has anyone ever called you by nasty names (loser, idiot, etc.) on social media?	68 (59.1)	41 (35.7)	6 (5.2)	115 (100)	1.46
Has anyone ever shared his/her sexual pictures to you without your consent on social media?	72 (62.6)	34 (29.6)	9 (7.8)	115 (100)	1.45
Has anyone ever through the social media threatened to injure you?	81 (70.4)	27 (23.5)	7 (6.1)	115 (100)	1.36
Have you ever been teased (laughter, make fun of) on social media?	74 (64.3)	37 (32.2)	4 (3.5)	115 (100)	1.39
Has anyone ever posted negative comments about you on their status updates on social media?	69 (60.0)	42 (36.5)	4 (3.5)	115 (100)	1.43
Have you ever been catfished (given false identity) on social media?	82 (71.3)	27 (23.5)	6 (5.2)	115 (100)	1.34
Have you ever been body shamed because of a picture you posted on social media?	82 (71.3)	28 (24.3)	5 (4.3)	115 (100)	1.33
Have you ever been criticized because of a post you made on your timeline?	69 (60.0)	39 (33.9)	7 (6.1)	115 (100)	1.46

Key: N= Not at all, S= Sometimes, A= Always

The component of respondents who have received negative comments about them on their status updates on social media, as well as those who have been subjected to false rumours was slightly significant. The two forms of cyberbullying had 40% and 39% respectively indicating that they sometimes or always receive these messages. Slightly over a third of the respondents (37%) indicated that they sometimes or always had their sexual pictures shared on social media without their consent. Another 36% of the respondents

indicated that they have sometimes or always been teased (laughter, make fun of) on social media.

The least popular forms of cyberbullying were being threatened with injury over social media; being catfished (given false identity) on social media; and being body shamed because of a picture posted on social media. All the three forms of cyberbullying had over 80% of the respondents indicating that they have never encountered these forms of cyberbullying.

Interview responses on the types of social media bullying varied, with all respondents noting the sharing of sexual pictures of victims without their consent. They also noted situations in which victims are continuously subjected to false rumours on social media, as well as either being teased, and receiving negative comments about them on their status updates. A social worker who was interviewed had this to say:

“Bullies are people who have low self-esteem or insecurities about themselves, and then they project that onto other people and use the power of social media because they are not seen; they only use their voices by typing whatever they want to say about people online. Based on the number of reported cases, females are the ones who are mostly bullied. They always cry about their pictures posted without their consent because they want to spite them and hurt them”.

Effects of cyberbullying on youth

The outcomes of the effects of bullying on the youth were listed, and the respondents were asked to tick the correct answers from not at all, sometimes, and always. The respondent's responses are presented in Table 2. Slightly over two thirds (67%) of the respondents indicated that they either sometimes (46%) or always (21%) feel upset because of social media bullying. This was followed by slightly above half (51%) who indicated that they feel anxious (nervous, rapid heartbeat, panicking) when certain things are posted on social media.

Table 2: Responses on the effects of bullying on youth of KSD local municipality

Statement	N	S	A	Total	Average
Do you have a negative feeling (low self-esteem) about yourself when you are on social media?	61 (53.0)	46 (40.0)	8 (7.0)	115 (100)	1.54
Do you feel upset because of social media bullying?	38 (33.0)	53 (46.1)	24 (20.9)	115 (100)	1.88
Do you have lack of self-confidence (feel not good enough) because of social media bullying?	73 (63.5)	37 (32.2)	5 (4.3)	115 (100)	1.41
Are you suicidal because of social media bullying?	103 (89.6)	9 (7.8)	3 (2.6)	115 (100)	1.13
Do you feel depressed (feeling sad, overwhelmed) because of social media?	74 (64.3)	37 (32.2)	4 (3.5)	115 (100)	1.39
Have you ever attempted to hurt yourself (cutting yourself) because of social media bullying?	101 (87.8)	9 (7.8)	5 (4.4)	115 (100)	1.17
Have you been having sleepless nights because of social media bullying?	87(75.7)	23(20.0)	5(4.3)	115 (100)	1.29
Do you feel anxious (nervous, rapid heartbeat, panicking) when certain things are posted on social media?	56 (48.7)	48 (41.7)	11 (9.6)	115 (100)	1.61
Has social media attack from peers brought lack of concentration that results in lower performance of at school?	77 (67.0)	34 (29.6)	4 (3.5)	115 (100)	1.37

Key: N= Not at all, S= Sometimes, A= Always

Though slightly below half (47%), a significant portion of respondents indicated that they sometimes or always have a negative feeling (low self-esteem) about themselves when they are bullied on social media. Another 36% apiece indicated that they sometimes or always have lack of self-confidence (feel not good enough), as well as feel depressed (feeling sad, overwhelmed) because of social media bullying. A third of the respondents indicated that they sometimes or always lack concentration that results in lower performance at school

as a result of social media bullying. Almost a quarter of the respondents (24.3%) indicated that they sometimes or always have sleepless nights because of social media bullying.

The least popular effects were an attempt by the victims to hurt themselves (cutting themselves) because of social media bullying and being suicidal because of social media bullying. Only 12% and 10%, respectively, indicated that they either sometimes or always witnessed these effects.

Interview participants reiterated most of the effects that were on the questionnaire, with the impact on the mental health, culminating in depression, fear, and poor performance in schools being the main effects that they pointed out. As regards the impact on school children, one of the interviewees indicated remarked, "...because of fear and not feeling safe, some victims even want to change schools because they do not want to see or meet the person bullying them".

Copying mechanisms for bullying on social media

This section shows the mechanisms of coping with bullying on social media. The mechanisms of coping with bullying on social media were listed, and the respondents were asked to select the correct answers from strongly disagree, disagree, agree, and strongly agree. The responses are presented in Table 3. Reporting cyberbullies accounts to minimize bullying on social media was considered as the main copying mechanism, with an overwhelming majority (72%) strongly agreeing to this copying mechanism, while 27% agreed. Closely following was use of passwords and privacy settings to minimize chances of accounts being used as a tool of cyberbullies, with 70% strongly agreeing to this copying mechanism.

Not sharing personal information on social networks to minimize social media bullying came third, with 61% strongly agreeing to the copying mechanism. Limiting people having access to users' profile to deter bullying on social media had 55% of the respondents strongly agreeing to the copying mechanism. Half of the respondents strongly agreed with speaking to professionals to help them cope with social media bullying. Not responding and retaliating on social networks to minimize social media bullying had 49% strongly agreeing.

Table 3: Responses on mechanisms of coping with social media bullying

Statement	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Total
Regulating time spent on social networks to minimize bullying on social media.	3 (2.6)	11 (9.6)	56 (48.7)	45 (39.1)	115 (100)
Limiting people having access to my profile deter bullying on social media.	0 (0)	7 (6.1)	45 (39.1)	63 (54.8)	115 (100)
Not responding and retaliating on social networks to minimize social media bullying.	3 (2.6)	9 (7.8)	47 (40.9)	56 (48.7)	115 (100)
Social support from my family members and friends helps me cope with social media bullying.	2 (1.7)	11 (9.6)	57 (49.6)	45 (39.1)	115 (100)
Protecting my passwords and privacy settings to minimize chances of my account being used as a tool of cyberbullies.	0 (0)	1 (0.9)	33 (28.7)	81 (70.4)	115 (100)
Speak to professionals to help me cope with social media bullying.	3 (2.6)	6 (5.2)	49 (42.6)	57 (49.6)	115 (100)
Report cyberbullies accounts to minimize bullying on social media.	0 (0)	1 (0.9)	31 (27.0)	83 (72.2)	115 (100)
Not sharing my personal information on social networks to minimize social media bullying.	0 (0)	3 (2.6)	42 (36.5)	70 (60.9)	115 (100)

Social support from family members and friends to help victims to cope with social media bullying, and regulating time spent on social networks to minimize bullying on social media had 39% apiece of the respondents strongly agreeing to these copying mechanisms. Overall, all the copying mechanisms were popular with the respondents, albeit with a different level of agreement to the mechanisms.

Interview participants also reiterated these varied copying mechanisms, with most of them emphasising the need for the youth to be vigilant on social media platforms, as well as for social media companies to play their part through ensuring privacy. Others

emphasised the need for awareness against cyberbullying at schools and homes. One of the participants succinctly summarised these views as follows;

“Technology companies are supposed to come up with tighter security measures that protect access to bullying. There must be restrictions on pictures, videos, and voice notes that are associated with bullying. There must be a way of picking them up and either being deleted or being unable to post such content. Also, English must not be the only language detected when someone has written something to bully others on the internet; other languages must also be detected. Now that we understand there is a problem, there must be psychoeducation at schools/ universities that addresses the danger and consequences of social media bullying. Lastly, online users must learn to focus on content only relevant to their social well-being”.

Discussion

Results of the study reveal the different manifestations of bullying on social media, with rude messages (for example, swearing) from fake accounts on social media being considered as the most dominant form of abuse. This form of bullying, which can be equated to masquerading (see Watts et al., 2017), is made possible by the unique capabilities of social media platforms. The ability to separate one’s real identity from the one a person uses on social media allows bullies to harm the victims because they know they will not be held accountable. Similarly, being called by nasty names such as loser and idiot, as well as being heavily criticised for posts on social media platforms were identified as other forms of bullying. Others also indicated having been victims of false rumours on social media platforms. Though not popular among questionnaire respondents, sharing of sexually explicit pictures without the victims’ consent was regarded by interview participants as a serious manifestation of cyberbullying. This form of cyberbullying is compounded by the fact that social media platforms can allow perpetrators to post the victim’s photos without their consent. Given the widely believed view that the youth spend most of their time on social media platforms (see Dube, 2016; Seo et al., 2014; Park & Gursoy, 2012), the exposure to cyberbullying will continue to endure. As the youth use social media platforms to build relationships, as well as to receive positive comments, they upload their photos and content which later become the subjects of bullying. As noted by Kusyanti and Safitiri (2019), the

more likes one gets on the pictures they upload, the more eager a user will be to upload more pictures. Moreover, despite having uploaded the photos and content with good intentions, the capabilities offered by some Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications make it possible for perpetrators to alter the victims' photos and content to suit their vile intentions. Ultimately, the youth upload their content online for the sake of having fun and fame, but inadvertently expose themselves to cyberbullies because of the content they post.

The results also reveal varying effects of bullying on social media platforms. Overall, feeling upset was regarded as the dominant effect of social media bullying. This is not surprising as the natural way of reacting to something unpleasant is to feel bad. As previously noted by Jackson & Cohen (2012) and Dehue et al. (2008), anger, distress and possession of weapons are some of the reactions to bullying on social media, all of which border around feeling upset. The study also revealed that most youth sometimes feel anxious (for example, nervousness, rapid heartbeat, panicking) when they are bullied on social media platforms. The aspect of anxiety is buttressed in earlier studies by Alden and Taylor (2021) and Nesi et al. (2015), who emphasised the social anxiety that is associated with being negatively evaluated or judged by others. Other leading impacts of social media bullying are feeling depressed and losing self-confidence, both of which are confirmed in the previous studies (see Jackson & Cohen, 2012; Faryadi, 2011; Dehue, Bolman & Vollink, 2008). With a third of the respondents indicating that they sometimes or always lack concentration at school, resulting in lower performance, this resonates with previous findings (Akcil, 2018; Faryadi, 2011; Walker et al., 2011), where it was established that the depression that accompanies cyberbullying reduces the students' ability to concentrate on their studies. The significant impact on educational performance was noted by all the interview participants, with some highlighting a sad scenario where some students opt to be transferred to other schools after falling victim to bullying on social media platforms. Contrary to some previous researchers' finding that committing suicide is one of the reactions to social media bullying (see Faryadi, 2011; Juvonen & Gross, 2008), findings reveal that self-infliction of harm through injuring oneself and committing suicide were the least impacts of social media bullying.

Findings also reveal that the victims have adopted different mechanisms to cope with incidents of bullying on social media

platforms. Reporting cyberbullies accounts to minimize bullying on social media was considered as the main coping mechanism. Given the capabilities of most social media platforms to report abuse of the platforms, accompanied by the ability of the social media service providers to block abusers, this logically becomes the most convenient option to respond to bullying on social media. Other popular coping mechanisms, which put the onus upon the social media users to be vigilant, include: use of privacy settings to minimize chances of accounts being accessed by cyberbullies; not sharing personal information on social networks; limiting people having access to users' profile; and not responding and retaliating on social networks. While these measures are crucial to minimise susceptibility to bullying on social networks, they may be difficult to adopt for the youth as they derive more fun from having more views and engagements with the broader online audience. Findings also reveal the importance of the family in dealing with bullying on social media. To this end, social support from family members and friends to help victims to cope with social media bullying, and regulating time spent on social networks to minimize bullying on social media were also regarded as important coping mechanisms, in resonance with Peled (2019) and Tanrikulu (2015)'s earlier findings. In order to regulate time spent on social networks, it is important to also involve the educational institutions, as previously recommended by Perren et al. (2012) and Walrave et al. (2012).

Conclusion

Results of the study reveal that quite a significant proportion of the youths have experienced bullying on social media platforms, and this is largely attributed to their heavy presence on social media platforms. The bullying mainly manifests through rude messages from fake accounts on social media accounts. Other significant manifestations include being called by nasty names such as loser and idiot; being heavily criticised for posts on social media platforms; false rumours on social media platforms; and sharing of sexually explicit pictures without the victims' consent. Results also revealed that social media bullying has significant negative impacts on the psycho-social wellbeing of the victims. Feeling upset, anxiety, depression and loss of self-confidence were found to be the leading effects of bullying on social media platforms. The negative impact of social media bullying on educational performance was also confirmed in this study. While vigilance, encompassing reporting abusers, blocking abusers and enhancing privacy safety measures

was regarded as the most important copying mechanisms, the central role of the family in monitoring social media activities and reducing exposure to social media platforms was also emphasised in this study.

In light of these findings, a multi-stakeholder approach to dealing with social media bullying is imperative. Social media service providers need to play their part by monitoring online content, as well as deleting or blocking cyber bullies' accounts. The youth need to be educated on the harmful consequences of bullying, with communities, educational institutions and churches playing a key role. Online presence for the youth needs to be strongly monitored by parents and school authorities and corrective action should immediately be taken when questionable online activities are identified.

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